

NUMBER OF GRAPHENE LAYERS IN NATURAL GRAPHITE

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Abstract

The article presents a model for determining the number of monolayers in graphite, which turned out to be equal to three monolayers. The presented model is universal and can determine the number of layers of any solids and even liquids. The model requires knowing the molar mass and density of the material. For graphene, this model is confirmed by the Raman method and other methods, which confirms the proposed model.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, surface layer, nanostructure, surface, delamination, crystal.

Introduction

The exfoliation (intercalation) of layered crystals using mica (muscovite - $KAl_3Si_3O_{12}H_2$) as an example was used by I.V. Obreimov back in 1930 [1] to determine the surface energy and adhesion energy of mica crystals. This method was implemented at a higher level in [2] and by us theoretically in [3]. Exfoliation of layered graphite crystals was carried out mechanically using adhesive tape in 2004 [4]. A single-layer graphite sheet was called graphene. However, it is impossible to use graphene obtained mechanically on an industrial scale. Therefore, various methods for obtaining graphene have appeared, a review of which is given in the monograph [5]. We also proposed a method for exfoliating layered graphite crystals with microcluster water

[6], the theoretical justification for which is given in [7, 8].

The purpose of this article is a theoretical model for determining the number of graphite layers and a comparison of this model with the Raman spectroscopy method.

Graphite

Graphite is a thermodynamically stable sp^2 -hybridized allotropic modification of carbon. The crystal structure of graphite [9] has hexagonal symmetry and consists of flat layers of carbon atoms located parallel to each other (Fig. 1a). The structure of graphite layers is shown in Fig. 1b, constructed according to the methodology of our work [10].

Figure 1. Graphite structure [9] (a); graphite layer structure [10] (b).

The R(I) layer is described by the method [10] by the equation:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu [m]. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) we need to know one parameter – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu =$

M/ρ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$ is a constant to maintain the dimensionality ($R(I) = [m]$). Using formula (1), we calculate R(I) (Table 1) for graphite parallel to the plane $x = a = b$ and perpendicular to this plane $x = c$.

Table 1.

Parameters R(I) of graphite [11].

Graphite	Structure	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm
C	C6/mmc-D _{6h} ⁴	12,0107	2,26	0.90 (3)	2.46 (3)

From Table 1 it is evident that the thickness of the $R(I)a$ layer is equal to: 0.9 nm in the upper plane and 2.46 nm perpendicular to this plane (Fig. 1a), i.e. it represents a nanostructure according to Gleiter [12]. In Table 1 the number of graphite monolayers is given in

brackets, equal to $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the constant of the graphite crystal lattice). It is evident that the number of monolayers in graphite is 3. This is confirmed by experimental data (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Change in graphene parameters depending on the number of its layers

Fig. 2a shows the change in internal pressure from the number of graphene layers [14]. Fig. 2b shows the intensity of the peak G of the Raman scattering of graphene from the number of its layers [15]. Fig. 2c shows the change in the coefficient of thermal expansion of graphene from the number of graphene layers [16]. Fig. 2d shows the sputtering intensity of the C₂⁻ ion, which increases abruptly with an increase in the number of graphene layers deposited on a copper substrate [17]. The presented figures show that graphite contains 3 graphene monolayers, which confirms our model (1). If we take into account that we obtained the formula [10]:

$$A(r) = A_0 \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{r} \right), \quad R(I) < r < R(II) \quad (2)$$

$$A(r) = A_0 \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + r} \right), \quad 0 < r < R(I).$$

where $A(r)$ is the physical property of the nano- and mesolayer; A_0 is the property of the volume; $r = z$

(Fig. 1 b). In the $R(I)$ layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer becomes equal to γ_1 [18]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + h} \right) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer is three times less than the surface energy of the main crystal. To separate the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the adhesion energy [19]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1,3\gamma_2, \quad (4)$$

where γ_{12} is the energy at the phase boundary, which is small due to the second-order phase transition. The internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 are calculated using the formula [19]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \bar{L} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus. Let's calculate the elastic parameters for graphite.

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite						
Carbon	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , MPa	σ_{isc} , MPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
Graphite	3,613	0,798	5740	1370	7,59	3,48

Let us now discuss the results of Raman spectroscopy. The Raman effect (Raman scattering) is a phenomenon of inelastic scattering of light. It was discovered by Raman in 1928. Raman spectroscopy is based on the Raman effect. In the 1960s, it underwent revolutionary changes with the introduction of lasers. In the second half of the 1970s, Raman spectroscopy in combination with an optical microscope began to be used

for microanalysis. In the 1990s, the first Raman confocal microscope was demonstrated. In 1998, SOLAR TII (SOL Instruments), Tokyo Instruments (TII) and NT-MDT jointly developed a 3D scanning Raman confocal microscope. The information obtained from the Raman spectra is shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Raman spectra	
Raman spectroscopy	Information
Peak position	Stress Strain Phase transition
Peak polarization	Crystal orientation Polymer orientation Symmetry
Peak width	Crystal quality Degree of crystallinity
Intensity	Material content Concentration
Characteristic frequencies	Material recognition Chemical analysis

A review of Raman spectroscopy of graphite, graphene and multilayer graphene is given in the works [18, 19]. An extensive bibliography on this subject is also given there. The review [18] discusses the shear, layer breathing, G and 2D modes of multilayer graphene with different stacking orders. Methods for determining the number of graphene layers, studying the resonance Raman spectra of monolayer and multilayer graphenes and obtaining Raman images of graphene-based materials are also presented. The review [19] shows that Raman spectroscopy is one of the main

methods for characterizing graphene and related materials. It is a non-destructive technique that can provide insight into the quality of the material, the number of layers and is sensitive to any changes in electric or magnetic fields, band structure and temperature, which makes it ideal for studying layered materials. Figure 3a shows the spectra of single-layer graphene (bottom) and graphite (top). In Fig. 3b shows a comparison of Raman spectra of graphite (3 monolayers) and graphene (one monolayer).

Figure 3. Raman spectra [19] (a); comparison of the 2D graphene and graphite bands [6] (b).

Fig. 4 shows the Raman spectra of multilayer graphene.

Figure 4. Raman spectra of graphene [19]

Figure 4 shows that the Raman spectrum does not change over 3 layers of graphene. We also recorded Raman spectra on a Solver Spectrum (NT-MDT). The results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Normalized Raman spectra of graphite (a) and graphene (b).

For final confirmation of the 3-layer surface layer of graphite, we will also present the data shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6.

Lateral force method in AFM (a); Kelvin probe force microscopy: surface potential in graphene (b) [20].

Thus, according to our model (1), graphite in the surface layer contains 3 monolayers, which differ from each other, as well as from the bulk phase as a whole.

A single-layer graphite sheet - graphene - is a unique material with properties such as a large theoretical spe-

cific surface area ($\sim 2600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) [21], high charge carrier mobility ($\sim 200,000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$) [22], high Young's modulus ($\sim 1000 \text{ GPa}$) [23], thermal conductivity ($\sim 5000 \text{ W/m K}$) [24], optical transparency ($\sim 97.7\%$) [25], mechanical strength, chemical stability, etc.

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite. It is actively studied [26] due to its controlled band gap. An analogue of bilayer graphene is Stone-Wales graphene or SW graphene, which is more stable in structure than graphene [27]. Three-layer

graphene differs from the latter two in mobility and conductivity [28]. A feature of three-layer graphene is that after its magic angle twisting, it develops superconductivity, which withstands magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [29]. Thus, all monolayers in a graphite nanolayer, as well as a solid as a whole, differ significantly from each other. We obtained graphene nanoflakes by intercalating graphite with microcluster water (MCW) (Fig. 7) and also studied using the Raman method.

Figure 7. Intercalation of graphite MCF (a); graphene nanoflakes (b).

Conclusion

The surface layer of graphite contains 3 monolayers of graphene, which differ from each other in their physical properties. This situation is also typical for metals, most of which have a number of monolayers from 2 to 6 (determined by equation (1)). The surface layer of a solid has only just begun to be intensively studied, so everything is still ahead.

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